

Foreword

The working group (WG) has been established by the European Commission with the aim to promote the use of NGS across the EURLs' networks, build NGS capacity within the European Union (EU) and ensure liaison with the work of the EURLs and the work of EFSA and ECDC on the NGS mandate sent by the Commission. The WG includes all the EURLs operating in the field of the microbiological contamination of food and feed and this document represents a deliverable of the WG and is meant to be diffused to all the respective networks of National Reference Laboratories (NRLs).

Guidelines for Dry-Lab Quality Control Metrics and Acceptance Thresholds in Short-Read WGS of zoonotic and indicator bacteria

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1 Introduction

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) enables rapid, cost-effective and high-throughput characterisation of microbial genomes. It is increasingly used in diagnostics and surveillance of foodborne and indicator bacteria. Common applications of WGS include (i) species identification, (ii) antimicrobial resistance (AMR) gene and associated mutation detection, (iii) virulence gene detection, (iv) serotype-associated genes detection and (v) outbreak investigations.

To ensure reliability and cross-laboratory comparability, implementation of standardised WGS protocols and rigorous quality control (QC) are essential. Relevant standards for both wet and dry components of WGS, as well as metadata management are included in **EN ISO 23418:2022** “Microbiology of the Food Chain – WGS for typing and genomic characterization of bacteria - General requirements and guidance”, **ISO 20397-1:2022** “Biotechnology – Massively parallel sequencing, Part 1: Nucleic acid and library preparation” and **ISO 20397-2:2021** “Biotechnology – Massively parallel sequencing, Part 2: Quality evaluation of sequencing data”.

This guidance document focus on dry lab QC for short-read WGS data of zoonotic and indicator bacteria and is intended to support National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) and official laboratories by defining QC criteria and accepted thresholds to the zoonotic and indicator bacteria covered by the European Union Reference Laboratories (EURLs) that are part of the Inter EURLs Working Group on NGS (Inter-EURLs WG on NGS). It describes measurable parameters for the dry-lab component and explains how their values affect downstream analyses and reporting.

This document serves as a reference for laboratories to enhance their WGS data quality and, consequently, the accuracy of zoonotic and indicator bacteria identification and characterisation.

2 Quality control across the WGS workflow

The Inter-EURLs WG on NGS considered the wet-lab and dry lab process (bioinformatics analyses) as two distinct processes, each requiring specific QC. Accordingly, QC should be performed during the following WGS phases:

- Preanalytical (DNA extraction and library preparation).
- Analytical (sequencing run quality), and
- Postanalytical (bioinformatics data processing).

Five QC checkpoints can be defined throughout the WGS process: DNA template QC, library QC, sequencing run QC, raw data QC and data analysis QC.

2.1 Wet lab component (out of scope here)

Guidance for obtaining high quality DNA for WGS have already been published by the Inter-EURLs WG on NGS in a separate document (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10409121>). Further details can also be found in EN ISO 23418:2022 and ISO 20397-1:2022.

2.2 Dry lab Component (scope of this document)

A detailed documentation of the dry lab component is critical to ensure good quality in WGS data. This document aims to provide guidance on QC parameters to be included. The dry lab analysis part typically consists of a number of steps including:

- Run-level quality assurance (QA) (instrument/run performance).
- Sample-level QC.
- Read pre-processing & raw-data QC (FASTQ-level).
- Coverage QC (depth and breadth).
- Contamination QC (inter- and intra-species).
- Assembly QC (when assemblies are used downstream).
- Typing-readiness QC (cgMLST gate + concordance flag for EURL using serotype).

Pipelines that combine several analysis steps and take raw and/or assembled sequencing data as input are often used. The pipelines will typically summarize the presence and characteristics of genetic markers and make phenotype predictions. They will also identify clusters of closely related

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isolates or make phylogenetic inferences based on 7-loci Multi-Locus Sequence Typing (MLST), cgMLST (core genome Multi-Locus Sequence Typing) allele profiles, SNPs (single nucleotide polymorphisms), or k-mer based distance methods.

The inferred relationships between isolates can be illustrated using phylogenetic trees, dendrograms, minimum spanning trees and distance matrices. For cgMLST analyses, reads are assembled or mapped. Target loci are identified, quality-filtered, and compared to curated cgMLST databases of allelic sequences. Such an approach for cluster analysis is in use in the EFSA One Health WGS System to inspect correlation among isolates, in particular during an outbreak situation.

3 Sequencing Quality Control

Sequencing technologies generate a high number of reads in a single experiment. However, errors may arise from low-quality sequencing data and should be addressed through trimming or quality control. Reads quality check can include several measures, including:

- Q-scores, e.g., Q30+ percentage and distribution over reads.
- Read-length.
- Base composition bias.
- GC content.
- Duplication level.
- Adapter contaminations.
- Ambiguous basecalls.
- Coverage depth.
- Contamination levels.

Read quality and quantity impact downstream assembly, read mapping, and the ability to use WGS data for bacterial source tracking and genome characterisation. Sequencing artifacts that can impact downstream analysis include:

- Platform-specific sequencing error profiles.
- Variation in quality scores across reads.
- Base composition-driven biases.
- Deviations from optimal library fragment sizes.
- Contamination from species other than the sequencing target.

Metrics and QC of sequences used to assess run performance should be assessed and documented at the completion of the sequencing run.

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Laboratories should test for contamination in sequencing data and determine thresholds appropriate for specific applications. Two different types of contaminations can occur, where either reads from an unrelated species (inter-species contamination) or reads from the same or a very closely related species (intra-species contamination) are present in the sequencing file. Different methods are available to check for contamination including:

- K-mer hashing against a reference sequence database.
- Calculating the average nucleotide identity (ANI) of sequence data.
- Checking for numbers of rDNA alleles in reads or assemblies.
- Verifying serotypes with bioinformatic serotype prediction tools.
- Comparing assemblies to reference databases.

Laboratories should determine and record their specifications for the quality assessment parameters. Criteria used for assessing sequence quality for an isolate can include:

- Average quality score.
- Number of reads and average read Phred score.
- Tests for contamination should be implemented and appropriate limits for contaminants (e.g., sequencing carryover or cross-contamination from sample preparation) should be determined that are acceptable for further bioinformatics analysis. Table 1 reports the contamination threshold defined by each EURL, as well as the software used.

For the bioinformatic pipelines using assemblies, the quality of the assemblies should be assessed before starting additional analysis. EURLs recommend the following measures as general indicators of assembly quality:

- Number of contigs. Low-coverage and/or small contigs may be removed before estimating assembly quality.
- N50 and/or NG50 and length of the longest contig.
- The genome size of the target organism verified by the total length of all contigs or scaffolds.
- For cgMLST approach, presence of species-specific conserved elements (e.g. core genome).

4 cgMLST analysis

The first step in the gene-by-gene analysis is to select an appropriate cgMLST-scheme to use for the analysis, i.e. a pathogen specific target list of genes to which all sequenced genomes will be compared. Within the EURL network, ChewBBACA is the most widely used tool (a tool also selected by EFSA in the One Health WGS system) (Silva *et al*, 2018) to perform allele calling from assembled genomes against the different schemas. To compare isolates, a threshold of 5% - 10% of missing loci is applied by the EURLs (Table 1). The cgMLST distance matrix is then used to identify whether isolates are closely related. A threshold of allelic difference (AD) is typically applied, which can vary between different bacterial species (and in some cases even serotypes), to define a cluster of related isolates.

5 Metrics of QC table provided by the EURLs

Table 1 summarises the various quality control steps during bioinformatics analysis used and/or recommended by each EURL for their respective microbiological hazard or topic. The steps highlighted in bold are considered to be the most critical ones. Thresholds used or recommended by the different EURLs are also included when appropriate.

Table 1: Tools and parameters for Quality Assessment of NGS data provided by the respective EURL (bold: Critical Metrics for each EURLs)

5.1 Antimicrobial Resistance (1/2)

Metric (raw reads or assembly level)	Definition	Tool + database version (if applicable)	Acceptance threshold(s)	Criticality ¹
Raw Reads: %Q_{≥30}	Fraction of bases with Phred ≥ 30 after adapter/quality trimming	Fastp v0.23.4 (report)	$\geq 80\%$ (read length 2x150 and shorter); $\geq 75\%$ (read length 2x250 and shorter); $\geq 70\%$ (read length 2x300 and shorter)	Critical
Raw Reads: Read-length distribution	Distribution of read lengths before adapter/quality trimming	fastp v0.23.4 (report)	2x150 bp: $>95\%$ at 150 bp; 2x250 bp: $>90-95\%$ at 250 bp; 2x300 bp (Rule 1): $<5\%$ <120 bp, $>50\%$ >150 bp; 300 bp (Rule 2): $>90\%$ at 300 bp	Determined but non-critical
Raw Reads: Residual adapters	% Reads with adapters after trimming	FastQC v0.12.1 + MultiQC v1.26	$\leq 0.1\%$	Determined but non-critical
Raw Reads: Ambiguous bases (%N)	Proportion of Ns in reads after trimming	FastQC v0.12.1 + MultiQC v1.26	$< 0.1\%$	Determined but non-critical
Raw Reads: GC% (reads) & ΔGC	GC% from trimmed reads vs. expected species GC (ΔGC)	FastQC v0.12.1 + MultiQC v1.26	ΔGC $< 4\%$ deviation from the expected GC-content for species analysed (QualiBact ² is used for species GC content)	Critical
Raw Reads: Coverage depth	Median number of sequencing reads aligning per base across the genome	Mosdepth v0.3.11 / samtools v1.22	$\geq 30\times$ (routine); $\geq 50\times$ (outbreak SNP analysis)	Critical
Raw Reads: Coverage breadth	Percentage of genome bases with depth $\geq T$	Mosdepth v0.3.11 / samtools v1.22	$\geq 95\%$ @10 \times (routine); $\geq 95-98\%$ @10 \times (outbreak SNP analysis)	Critical
Raw Reads: Inter-species contamination/ Species confirmation	% of post-trim reads classified not to belong to the expected species (genus/species level)	Kraken2 v2.1.6 (Kraken2-microbial-30GB database) + Bracken v3.1	$< 5.0\%$ reads identified as non-target species	Critical

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Metric (raw reads or assembly level)	Definition	Tool + database version (if applicable)	Acceptance threshold(s)	Criticality ¹
Raw Reads: Intra-species mixture	Same-species mix indicated by >1 allele in single-copy core genes within a sample	ConFindr v0.8.2 (PubMLST rMLST database 2025-03-14)	No multiple-allele calls (flag if any)	Determined but non-critical
Assembly : Species confirmation	Species ID by k-mer matching against curated DB	KmerFinder v3.0.2 (bitbucket database 2022-07-11)	Concordant with expected sample metadata	Critical
Assembly : Size (Mb)	Total assembly length	QUAST v5.3.0	Within species range (QualiBact ² is used for species cutoffs)	Critical
Assembly: Contiguity: N50 / #contigs	N50 (kb) and number of contigs (≥0 bp)	QUAST v5.3.0	Species-specific thresholds (QualiBact ² is used for species cutoffs)	Determined but non-critical
Metric (raw reads or assembly level)	Definition	Tool + database version (if applicable)	Acceptance threshold(s)	Criticality ¹
Assembly: GC%	Assembly GC%	QUAST v5.3.0	Within species-typical range (QualiBact ² is used for species cutoffs)	Determined but non-critical
Assembly: Ns per 100 kb	Number of ambiguous bases (N) per 100,000 bp in the assembled genome	QUAST v5.3.0	≤100 Ns/100 kb (preferably close to 0) (contig-only bacterial assemblies)	Determined but non-critical
Assembly: Single-copy marker completeness/contamination	Genome completeness & contamination via marker sets	CheckM2 v1.1.0	Completeness ≥95%; Contamination ≤5%	Critical
Typing readiness: cgMLST callable loci %	% Target loci with accepted allele calls	chewieSnake v3.2.1 (pipeline) / chewBBACA v2.0.12; cgMLST schema: Enterobase, PubMLST, or Ridom SeqSphere (genus/species dependent)	≥90–95% loci called (scheme/species-specific)	Critical

¹, **About the criticality:** QC metrics are categorized as either critical (pipeline stop criteria) or non-critical (flagged for review). Critical failures indicate the sample does not meet minimum quality requirements and must not be used for downstream analysis. Flagged metrics may proceed but should be documented and monitored.

², To access QualiBact thresholds go to <https://happykhan.github.io/qualibact/>.

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5.2 Campylobacter

QC steps	<i>Campylobacter</i>
Species confirmation:	<p style="text-align: center;">Kraken2 (8Gb standard database) followed by Bracken Evaluating top species hit</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Alternatively: Mash screen – (RefSeq database). Evaluating top score hit (score = identity x fraction shared hashes)</p>
Reads QC: Fastqc or Fastp	Fastp (alternatively FastQC) Amount of Q30+ bases should correspond to >=30X
Trimming:	Fastp (--detect_adapter_for_pe --cut_right --trim_poly_g --length_required 36) >=30X Q30+ data with no adapter sequences should be present after trimming
Downsampling:	BBmap reformat (samplebasestarget=100xgenomesize=170 000 000)
Contamination (inter species):	<p style="text-align: center;">Kraken2 (8 Gb standard database) followed by Bracken Evaluating second species hit Cross-hits between <i>C. jejuni</i> and <i>C. coli</i> are not deemed as contamination Contamination level should be below 5%</p>
Contamination (intra species):	Evaluated by number of paralogous hits in chewBBACA (NIPH+NIPHEM <=10)
Assembly QC:	<p style="text-align: center;">Quast: N50 >=10 kb Contigs <= 200 Assembly size (<i>C. jejuni</i> and <i>C. coli</i>): 1.4 Mb – 2.3 Mb</p> <p style="text-align: center;">CheckM: completedness >95% contamination <=5%</p>
Tool for cgMLST calling	ChewBBACA: (--no-inferred) MLST (fastMLST)
Schema used for cgMLST	Schema: PubMLST <i>C. Jejuni/C. coli</i> cgMLST v2 Hashing crc32 – in-house hashing script
Accepted % missing cgMLST loci	5%
% GC content	

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5.3 Coagulase Positive Staphylococci

QC steps	Coagulase Positive Staphylococci
Species confirmation	Mash
Reads QC: Fastqc or Fastp	Fastp
Reads QC: Minimum percent of High Quality of read (%)	≥ 80%
Reads QC: tool_contamination_threshold	Kraken2 ≤ 2% Confindr ≤ 7%
Q30 threshold (%)	–
Minimum depth (X)	50X
Assembly QC: N50 threshold (bp)	Determined but not critical
Assembly QC: N. contigs threshold	Determined but not critical
Assembly QC: Min genome size (Mbp)	2.6
Assembly QC: Max genome size (Mbp)	2.9
Tool for cgMLST calling	ChewBBACA
Schema used for cgMLST	Ridom® SeqSphere (Leopold)
Accepted % missing cgMLST loci	5-10%
% GC content	Determined but not critical

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5.4 Escherichia coli

QC steps	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Species confirmation	Kmerfinder
Reads QC: Fastqc or Fastp	Fastqc Fastp
Reads QC: Minimum percent of High Quality of read (%)	–
Reads QC: tool_contamination_threshold	Query coverage < 4 kmerfinder
Q30 threshold (%)	Determined but not critical
Minimum depth (X)	30X
Assembly QC: N50 threshold (bp)	Determined but not critical
Assembly QC: N. contigs threshold	Determined but not critical
Assembly QC: Min genome size (Mbp)	4.0
Assembly QC: Max genome size (Mbp)	Determined but not critical
Tool for cgMLST calling	ChewBBACA
Schema used for cgMLST	ChewieNS
Accepted % missing cgMLST loci	10%
% GC content	Determined but not critical

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5.5 *Listeria monocytogenes*

QC steps	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>
Species confirmation	Mash
Reads QC: Fastqc or Fastp	Fastp
Reads QC: Minimum percent of High Quality of read (%)	≥ 80%
Reads QC: tool_contamination_threshold	Kraken2 ≤ 2% Confindr ≤ 2%
Q30 threshold (%)	—
Minimum depth (X)	50X
Assembly QC: N50 threshold (bp)	Determined but not critical
Assembly QC: N. contigs threshold	Determined but not critical
Assembly QC: Min genome size (Mbp)	2.8
Assembly QC: Max genome size (Mbp)	3.2
Tool for cgMLST calling	ChewBBACA / Ridom® SeqSphere
Schema used for cgMLST	ChewieNS (Moura) and Ridom® SeqSphere (Ruppitsch)
Accepted % missing cgMLST loci	5%
% GC content	

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5.6 Salmonella

QC steps	<i>Salmonella</i>
Species confirmation	Kraken2 and bracken on contigs and reads
Reads QC: Fastqc or Fastp	Fastqc Fastp
Reads QC: Minimum percent of High Quality of read (%)	–
Reads QC: tool_contamination_threshold	CheckM ≤ 4%
Q30 threshold (%)	–
Minimum depth (X)	30X
Assembly QC: N50 threshold (bp)	≥ 30 000
Assembly QC: N. contigs threshold	≤ 300
Assembly QC: Min genome size (Mbp)	4.4
Assembly QC: Max genome size (Mbp)	5.8
Tool for cgMLST calling	ChewBBACA / Ridom® SeqSphere
Schema used for cgMLST	Chewie-NS / EnteroBase <i>S. enterica</i> cgMLST v2
Accepted % missing cgMLST loci	5%
% GC content	

6 Conclusion

The performance characteristics of WGS-based methods must be established for the intended use. Validation of the WGS workflow can be carried separately for the different components, but the complete workflow must be fully validated. The validation will provide evidence that the method is repeatable, reproducible, and accurate.

7 Tools cited in this document

BBduk2: <https://github.com/BioInfoTools/BBMap/blob/master/sh/bbduk2.sh>

Braken: <https://github.com/jenniferlu717/Bracken>

Confindr: <https://github.com/OLC-Bioinformatics/ConFindr>

CheckM: <https://github.com/Ecogenomics/CheckM>

ChewBBACA: <https://github.com/B-UMMI/chewBBACA>

FastQC: <https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>

Fastp: <https://github.com/OpenGene/fastp>

Kmerfinder: <https://github.com/albertwcheng/KmerFinder>

Kraken2: <https://ccb.jhu.edu/software/kraken/MANUAL.html>

Mash: <https://github.com/marbl/Mash>

MLST: <https://github.com/tseemann/mlst>

Query coverage: <https://github.com/gitmatheus/QueryCodeCoverage>

SeqSphere: <https://www.ridom.de/seqsphere/>

Shovill: <https://github.com/tseemann/shovill>

Trimmomatic: <https://github.com/usadellab/Trimmomatic>

Unicycler: <https://github.com/rrwick/Unicycler>

QUAST: <https://github.com/ablab/quast>